

Statistical Analysis of Galaxy Spin Vector Orientations in SDSS DR-18: Implications for Large-Scale Structure Formation

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Abstract We present a statistical analysis of galaxy spin vector orientations using $\sim 250,000$ galaxies from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) DR-18 within $0.10 < z < 0.15$. Three-dimensional rotation axes were derived via the position angle–inclination method from observed two-dimensional parameters. To correct for selection biases, 10^7 simulated galaxies were generated using a MATLAB-based model. The sample was divided into twenty *i*- and *u*-band magnitude subsamples, and isotropy was tested using chi-square, auto-correlation, and Fourier statistics. The majority of subsamples show isotropic polar (θ) and azimuthal (ϕ) angle distributions, indicating random spin orientations. However, specific subsamples exhibit mild anisotropies, likely caused by local tidal interactions or environmental effects. Polar distributions are largely isotropic, whereas azimuthal projections sometimes align toward the equatorial center. Overall, galaxy spin vectors are predominantly randomly oriented, consistent with the **Hierarchy model** of galaxy formation, while localized deviations support limited **Pancake-like** alignments. These results suggest that cosmic angular momentum generation is primarily stochastic, modulated by local gravitational interactions influencing galaxy orientation.

Key words: galaxies, evolution galaxies, formation galaxies, statistics galaxies, structure galaxies, redshifted

1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding the spatial orientation of galaxy spin vectors is fundamental to the study of cosmic structure formation and evolution. The angular momentum of galaxies is a key parameter that encodes information about their dynamical history, the large-scale tidal fields they have experienced, and the cosmological processes that shaped their morphology. Whether galaxies exhibit a preferred orientation or are randomly aligned provides crucial insight into the mechanisms driving the formation of large-scale structures in the Universe (Peebles 1969; Fall & Efstathiou 1980; White 1984).

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Over the past few decades, several theoretical frameworks have been proposed to explain the origin and distribution of galactic angular momentum. The **Hierarchy model** posits that galaxies acquire their spin through random tidal torques during the hierarchical clustering of dark matter halos, predicting an overall isotropic distribution of spin orientations (White 1984; Catelan & Theuns 1996). In contrast, the **Pancake model** suggests that galaxies form through the collapse of large-scale sheets of matter, potentially inducing partial alignments of spin vectors perpendicular to the plane of collapse (Doroshkevich 1973; Allan Sandage & Yahil 1978). The **Turbulence model** further proposes that initial cosmic turbulence could imprint coherent rotational features on galaxies (Oyama 1976). Observationally, the challenge lies in distinguishing these effects and determining whether galaxy spins exhibit statistically significant deviations from isotropy.

The Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) provides a vast, homogeneous, and high-quality dataset for such studies. The eighteenth data release (SDSS DR-18) offers precise photometric and spectroscopic measurements for millions of galaxies, making it possible to statistically probe the orientation of spin vectors across different redshift and magnitude ranges. Despite numerous earlier investigations (Godłowski 1993; Flin & Godłowski 1994; I. Trujillo & Frenk 2006), the dependence of spin vector orientation on galaxy brightness and redshift has not been thoroughly explored using the most recent SDSS datasets.

In this work, we analyze a sample of approximately 250,488 galaxies from SDSS DR-18 within the redshift range $0.10 < z < 0.15$. Using the **position angle–inclination method** (Flin & Godłowski 1986), we reconstruct the three-dimensional orientation of galaxy rotation axes from their observed two-dimensional parameters, namely right ascension, declination, position angle, and apparent axial ratio. To minimize observational selection effects, we developed a dedicated MATLAB-based simulation that generates 10^7 virtual galaxies for statistical comparison.

The galaxies are divided into twenty magnitude-based subsamples according to their *i*- and *u*-band photometric measurements. The orientation distributions of polar (θ) and azimuthal (ϕ) angles are then tested for isotropy using **Fourier**, **chi-square**, and **auto-correlation** statistics following the methodology of (Godłowski 1993, 1994). Deviations from isotropy are interpreted in the context of different galaxy formation models—namely the Hierarchy, Pancake, and Turbulence scenarios.

The primary aim of this study is to determine whether galaxies in the selected redshift range exhibit a preferred orientation of their spin vectors or if they are distributed randomly in space. By examining the magnitude and redshift dependence of spin vector orientations, we seek to constrain the role of environmental effects and local gravitational interactions in the evolution of galactic angular momentum.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the data and selection criteria; Section 3 details the methods used to derive the three-dimensional spin orientations; Section 4 presents the statistical analysis of the polar and azimuthal angle distributions; and Section 5 summarizes the major findings and discusses their implications for models of galaxy evolution and large-scale structure formation.

2 OBSERVATIONS

In this work we have used near Infra-red filter (*i*) and Ultraviolet filter (*u*) magnitude to analyze the database of blue-shifted galaxies. For *i*-filter and *u*-filter, SDSS' filters work best at wavelengths 7625 Å and 3543 Å respectively. Here we describe the data selection process for *u*-filter of second bin (Almeida & et al. 2023;

Table 1: Characteristics of Gaussian distribution for i and u filter in different subsamples.

Subsample	Name of filter	Mean	Standard deviation	Offset
$i01$	i	16.57897	1.05587	0
$u01$	u	19.84000	1.37800	0.09033
$i02$	i	16.83645	0.86785	0
$u02$	u	19.65743	1.28069	0.41241
$i03$	i	16.91528	0.80168	0.59179
$u03$	u	19.43588	1.14484	0

Abdurro'uf & et al. 2022).

Firstly, we selected all parameters associated with the u -filter and removed all the galaxies that do not have complete values of major and minor diameters and other parameters. Then we plotted the histogram of u -filter magnitude and fitted a Gaussian with minimum offset. Then galaxies with magnitude above twice the standard deviation were removed (Eisenstein & et al. 2011; Blanton & et al. 2017; Aguado & et al. 2019).

Fig. 1: The distribution of galaxies through i -filter(a) and u -filter(b). The solid line represents the Gaussian fit.

3 DATA REDUCTION

3.1 Selection Effects in the Database

The information we acquired includes the position angle, major and minor axes, latitude, and longitude (Holmberg 1946; Flin & Godlowski 1999). The 2-D projection of the galaxies on the celestial sphere's surface is described in these data. We must create the 3-D information about the galaxies from the 2-D data in order to investigate the orientation of the spin vectors in space (Shamir 2020, 2022). The following formulas could be used to calculate these angles (Flin & Godlowski 1986):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sin \theta &= -\cos i \sin \delta \pm \sin i \sin P \cos \delta, \\
 \sin \phi &= \frac{-\cos i \cos \delta \sin \alpha + \sin i (\mp \sin P \sin \delta \sin \alpha \mp \cos P \cos \alpha)}{\cos \theta}, \\
 \cos \phi &= \frac{-\cos i \cos \delta \cos \alpha + \sin i (\mp \sin P \sin \delta \cos \alpha \pm \cos P \sin \alpha)}{\cos \theta}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Table 2: A sample of our database from the subsample $u02$. Here i represents the inclination angle calculated from major and minor diameters. A complete list of our database is added in CD provided with this dissertation.

ra	dec	petroMag_u	isoA_u	isoB_u	i	isoPhi_u	z
219.518243	31.0680265	21.078995	5.386221	1.106534	87.21806538	133.93866	-0.000149
228.357514	31.9960266	21.071953	10.452889	2.199507	86.13815041	161.40691	-0.000110
168.693964	20.6433369	19.432119	26.562325	3.578229	84.76112597	30.28720	-0.000184
236.179584	57.5435423	20.165243	15.506208	3.407306	84.63557457	26.60562	-0.000135
244.398747	31.7671115	16.729181	303.928894	66.800919	84.62805458	32.21188	-0.000179
127.929979	11.1241241	21.210714	15.940380	2.189383	84.53618076	117.23259	-0.000133
233.701816	12.4223125	21.752748	6.352279	1.404423	84.44675328	15.43703	-0.000184
122.148201	39.9291810	21.782001	6.917882	0.959903	84.41803281	65.80879	-0.000120
182.093744	16.2184924	19.918116	31.140593	7.025693	83.84920846	91.70435	-0.000133
211.505697	15.1814294	20.569616	19.966921	4.552911	83.54860639	89.75634	-0.000136
241.577816	8.2369608	21.367714	18.674122	4.333889	83.06517777	46.06175	-0.000110
224.307341	18.3410014	21.317034	21.279318	5.023718	82.61100514	133.00020	-0.000125
222.166481	30.3635861	21.286697	4.457827	1.060908	82.40195370	55.71446	-0.000098
233.222005	1.0269428	18.869463	21.836315	5.260030	82.09110974	92.65306	-0.000174
219.318732	39.3990439	20.468332	10.226817	2.484617	81.87427244	70.85148	-0.000098
180.809310	56.6657444	21.107965	9.331398	2.283205	81.69577339	75.00248	-0.000162
185.731035	12.3375429	21.015081	18.936457	4.634491	81.68970133	145.61099	-0.000109
221.850325	26.0420165	18.861181	23.245121	5.707014	81.61047462	173.86807	-0.000154
209.041258	37.2550414	18.284245	29.725666	7.416709	81.20997358	142.27562	-0.000105
146.244306	64.9367875	12.710147	301.090729	57.101181	80.64730494	148.49820	-0.000139

The inclination angle, declination angle, right ascension angle, and position angle are denoted by i , δ , α , and P , respectively (Lee et al. 2019).

The angle between the observer's line of sight and the normal to the galaxy plane is known as the inclination angle i , and it may be found using the formula:

$$\cos^2 i = \frac{q^2 - q_*^2}{1 - q_*^2} \quad (2)$$

1. Inhomogeneous distribution of positions of galaxies,
2. Lack of knowledge of position angle of face-on galaxies, and
3. Lack of edge-on galaxies.

Fig. 2: The distributions of right ascension (α), declination (δ), position angle (P), and inclination angle (i) of the galaxies in the subsample *u02*. The y-axes of histograms represent the number of observed galaxies.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

We have classified our database into twenty samples on the basis of their redshift values and u & i -magnitudes. Here we discuss the distribution of the polar (θ) and azimuthal (ϕ) angles of galaxy rotation axes in each sample. We study the spatial orientation of spin vectors of galaxies with respect to the equatorial coordinate system. Any deviation from the expected isotropic distribution will be tested using four statistical parameters, namely the chi-square probability ($P > \chi^2$), auto-correlation coefficient ($C/C(\sigma)$), first order Fourier coefficient ($\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$), and first order Fourier probability ($P > \Delta_1$). For anisotropy, the limit of chi-square probability ($P > \chi^2$) is < 0.050 , auto-correlation coefficient ($C/C(\sigma)$) is > 1.0 , first order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ is > 1.5 and the Fourier probability ($P > \Delta_1$) is < 0.150 respectively. These statistical limits were proposed by Godlowski (1993, 1994) in galaxy orientation studies. Any ‘humps’ or ‘dips’ in the histogram will be discussed as a local effect in samples or a result

of binning or selection effects. Here ‘hump’ and ‘dip’ are defined as having more or fewer solutions than expected in a bin respectively.

Table 3: Statistics of the polar angle (θ) distribution of galaxies in different samples. The columns list: chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$, auto-correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$, first order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$, and Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$.

Sample	$P(> \chi^2)$	$C/C(\sigma)$	$\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$	$P(> \Delta_1)$
<i>i01</i>	0.50	+0.90	+1.91	0.145
<i>i02</i>	0.00	+56.09	+13.53	0.00
<i>i03</i>	0.68	-1.44	-0.014	0.994
<i>i04</i>	0.00	+76.07	+14.52	0.00
<i>i05</i>	0.00	+67.85	+14.42	0.00
<i>i06</i>	0.00	+42.90	+11.82	0.00
<i>i07</i>	0.00	+65.61	+14.66	0.00
<i>i08</i>	0.00	+54.75	+13.26	0.00
<i>i09</i>	0.00	+2299.266	+52.176	0.00
<i>i10</i>	0.00	+44.51	+11.81	0.00
<i>i11</i>	0.00	+51.73	+13.12	0.00
<i>i12</i>	0.00	+60.32	+13.93	0.00
<i>i13</i>	0.00	+61.26	+13.86	0.00
<i>i14</i>	0.00	+29.46	+9.67	0.00
<i>i15</i>	0.00	+41.28	+9.53	0.00
<i>i16</i>	0.00	+29.68	+6.21	0.00
<i>i17</i>	0.87	+0.25	+0.20	0.96
<i>i18</i>	0.00	+9.95	+5.62	0.00
<i>i19</i>	0.00	+14.79	+6.92	0.00
<i>i20</i>	0.02	-1.44	-0.189	0.76

The statistics for the polar angle (θ) and azimuthal angle (ϕ) distribution is given in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. In the statistics of θ , a negative value of first order Fourier coefficient suggests that the spin vectors of galaxies tend to be oriented perpendicular with respect to the equatorial coordinate system. Similarly, a positive value of first order Fourier coefficient suggests that the spin vectors of galaxies tend to be oriented parallel with respect to the equatorial coordinate system (Hahn & et al. 2007; Libeskind & et al. 2013). Whereas, in the statistics of ϕ , a positive $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ with significant value suggests that the spin vector projections of galaxies tend to point radially towards the center of the equatorial coordinate system. Similarly, a significant negative value of $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ implies that the spin vector projection of galaxies tend to orient tangentially with respect to the equatorial coordinate system (White 1984; Peebles 1969).

Table 4: Statistics of the azimuthal angle (ϕ) distribution of galaxies in the different subsamples. The first column lists the subsamples. The second, third, fourth, and fifth column list the corresponding chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$, auto-correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$, the first order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$, the first order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$, and standard deviation of Fourier amplitude $\sigma(\Delta_1)$ respectively.

Sample	$P(> \chi^2)$	$C/C(\sigma)$	$\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$	$P(> \Delta_1)$
<i>i01</i>	0.00	+3.13	+2.84	0.00
<i>i02</i>	0.00	+84.	+18.1	0.00
<i>i03</i>	0.00	+19.2	+0.89	0.34
<i>i04</i>	0.00	+140.1	+24.8	0.00
<i>i05</i>	0.00	+131.9	+22.8	0.00
<i>i06</i>	0.00	+105.8	+21.16	0.00
<i>i07</i>	0.00	+194.5	+26.31	0.00
<i>i08</i>	0.00	+151.5	+23.78	0.00
<i>i09</i>	0.00	+2117.6	+74.95	0.00
<i>i10</i>	0.00	+385.44	+38.42	0.00
<i>i11</i>	0.00	+117.9	+14.6	0.00
<i>i12</i>	0.00	+122.6	+15.21	0.00
<i>i13</i>	0.00	+95.7	+13.08	0.00
<i>i14</i>	0.00	+41.1	+9.63	0.00
<i>i15</i>	0.00	+436.9	+38.22	0.00
<i>i16</i>	0.00	+44.4	+13.00	0.00
<i>i17</i>	0.00	+143.5	+23.09	0.00
<i>i18</i>	0.00	+11.2	+6.30	0.00
<i>i19</i>	0.00	+16.9	+8.85	0.00
<i>i20</i>	0.71	-0.59	-0.13	0.951

In the histogram of the θ -distribution (see Fig.a as an example), solid curve represents the expected isotropic distribution whereas dashed curve is the cosine distribution. The solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars represent the observed distribution. The shaded portion represents the range $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$. A dip (or hump) at $\theta < 45^\circ$ suggests that the spin vectors of galaxies tend to orient perpendicular (or parallel) with respect to the equatorial coordinate system. Similarly, a hump (or dip) in the larger θ ($\theta > 45^\circ$) indicates that the spin vectors of galaxies tend to be oriented perpendicular with respect to the equatorial coordinate system(Dubois & et al. 2014).

In the histogram of the θ -distribution (see Fig. 5.1.1a as an example), the solid curve represents the expected isotropic distribution, whereas the dashed curve corresponds to the cosine distribution. The solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars represent the observed distribution. The shaded region represents the range $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$. A dip (or hump) at $\theta < 45^\circ$ suggests that the spin vectors of galaxies tend to orient perpendicular (or parallel) with respect to the equatorial coordinate system. Similarly, a hump (or dip) at larger θ values ($\theta > 45^\circ$) indicates that the spin vectors of galaxies tend to be oriented perpendicular with respect to the equatorial coordinate system(Ganeshiah Veena & et al. 2020).

In the histogram of the ϕ -distribution (see Fig.b as an example), the solid curve represents the expected isotropic distribution, whereas the dashed curve corresponds to the average distribution. The solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars represent the observed distribution. The shaded region represents the range $-45^\circ < \phi < +45^\circ$. In this case, $\phi = 0^\circ$ means that the spin vector projections of galaxies tend to point radially towards the center of the equatorial coordinate system. A hump in the middle of the histogram suggests that the spin vector projections of galaxies tend to point towards the center of the chosen coordinate system. On the other hand, a hump in the first four or last four bins indicates that the spin vector projections of galaxies tend to be oriented tangentially with respect to the chosen reference coordinate system.

4.0.1 Sample *i*14.00 to 15.00

Fig. 3: The *z*01 sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics. The θ distribution for Sample *i*01 appears to be isotropic according to all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta)$ is 14.5 percent and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ is 50 percent. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are determined to be under the 1σ error limit. It is evident from figure ??a that there are a hump and two notable dips. with the exception of a minor dip at $47^\circ, 65^\circ$, and a slight hump at 40° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs, though. As a result, sample *i*01's galaxies' angular momentum vectors do not exhibit any preferential alignment with regard to the equatorial coordinate system (Krolewski & et al. 2021).

Anisotropy in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in all three statistics (Table 4) for subsample *i*01. The first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to be 0 and 0 percent, respectively. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ have an error limit of $< 1\sigma$. $-45^\circ, -28^\circ, +15^\circ, +25^\circ, +45^\circ$, and $+35^\circ$ and $+50^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ, +86^\circ$. These ups and downs, however, have little effect on the overall sample statistics. Additionally, there is significant anisotropy in the correlation coefficient (Tempel et al. 2014). Thus, these

could be the result of binning. For subsample $i01$, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Thus, we conclude random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies.

4.0.2 Sample $i15.00$ to 15.50

Fig. 4: The $z02$ sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics. The θ distribution for Sample $i02$ appears isotropic according to all three statistical tests (Table 3). The first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are both 0 percent. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are within the 1σ error limit.

Figure a shows four humps and seven notable dips, except for slight humps at 3° , 10° , 13° , 15° and slight dips at 45° , 52° , 57° , 62° , 67° , 73° , 78° . These ups and downs do not affect the overall statistics. Therefore, the galaxies in sample $i02$ do not show any preferential alignment with respect to the equatorial coordinate system. For sample $i02$, all three statistics for azimuthal angles (Table 4) indicate an anisotropic distribution. The first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are both 0 percent. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ remain below the 1σ error limit. As shown in Fig.b, dips occur at $+55^\circ$, $+60^\circ$, $+75^\circ$, and $+85^\circ$, while humps appear at -45° , -35° , -28° (twice), -15° , -10° , and $+15^\circ$. These variations have little effect on the overall statistics and may result from binning. Thus, the spin vector projections of galaxies in sample $i02$ appear randomly oriented.

We therefore conclude that the galaxies' spin vectors and spin vector projections are randomly oriented. Although the correlation test indicates some local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropy. However, the spin vector projections of galaxies tend to point toward the equatorial center.

4.0.3 Sample $i15.50$ to 16.00

Fig. 5: The $z03$ sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics. The θ distribution for Sample $i03$ is an-isotropic according to all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is discovered that the first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta)$ is 99 percent and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ is 68 percent. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ is determined to be below the 1σ error limit, but the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ is not. Figure a, displays a hump and two noticeable dips. Except for a minor hump at 23° , a dip at 8° , and a 33° . The total sample statistics are not significantly impacted by those variations, though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample $i03$ do not exhibit any preferential alignment with regard to the equatorial coordinate system.

The azimuthal angle distribution for sample $i03$ exhibits a considerable isotropic according to all three statistics (Table 4). It is discovered that the first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are 34 percent and 0 percent, respectively. $< 1\sigma$ is the error limit for the correlation coefficient and the first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$. There are dips at $+50^\circ$, $+60^\circ$, $+75^\circ$, $+86^\circ$, and humps at -45° , -32° , -20° , -15° , $+10^\circ$, $-$. However, these oscillations alter the statistics of the overall sample. Additionally, there is noticeable an-isotropic in the correlation coefficient. Thus, these could be the result of binning. The galaxies in sample $i03$ have randomly oriented spin vector projections.

Consequently, we deduce that galaxies' spin vectors and spin vector projections are oriented arbitrarily. Although the correlation test indicates the presence of local effects, the polar angle distribution usually exhibits isotropy. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically face the equatorial center.

4.0.4 Sample *i16.00 to 16.25*

Fig. 6: The *z04* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The statistics is given in the (Table 3) all three statistical tests suggest isotropic in θ distribution for Sample *i04* (Table 3). The chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ and first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta)$ are found to be 0 and 0 percent respectively. The correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ and the first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ are not found to be 1σ error limit. From (Fig.a), we can see that there are seven significant dip and six hump. except a small dip at $50^\circ, 57^\circ, 62^\circ, 68^\circ, 73^\circ, 78^\circ, 83^\circ$ and hump at $5^\circ, 9^\circ, 15^\circ, 18^\circ, 20^\circ, 25^\circ$. However, those humps and dips change the statistics of the total sample. Hence, there is preferred alignment of angular momentum vectors of galaxies in sample *i04* with respect to equatorial coordinate system.

All two statistics (Table 4) for sample *i04* show isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution. The chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ and first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ are found to be 0 percent respectively. The correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ and the first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limit. There are humps at $-45^\circ, -34^\circ, -28^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, 3^\circ, 15^\circ, 27^\circ$ and dips at $-88^\circ, -85^\circ, -72^\circ, +50^\circ, +65^\circ, +72^\circ, +86^\circ$ (Fig. b). However, these humps and dips do not change the statistics of total sample. Also, the correlation coefficient and first-order Fourier coefficient shows strong an-isotropic. So, these are possibly the effect of binning. The random orientation for spin vector projections of galaxies is observed for sample *i04*. Thus, we conclude random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies.

In general, polar angle distribution shows isotropic, however correlation test shows the presence of local effects. On the other hand, spin vector projection of galaxies tend to point towards the equatorial center. This finding supports the pancake model of galaxy evolution.

Fig. 7: The $z05$ sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

4.0.5 Sample $i16.25$ to 16.38

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of θ distribution for Sample $i05$ appears to be isotropic according to all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are 0 percent, respectively. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit.

(Fig.a) shows that there are six humps and five notable dips, save for a minor hump at 4° , 8° , 13° , 18° , 23° , 27° , and a slight dip at 57° , 62° , 67° , 72° , 78° . But the ups and downs alter the overall sample's statistics. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample $i06$ are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system. For sample $i05$, both statistics (Table 4) demonstrate isotropy in the distribution of azimuthal angles. The first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to be 0 and 0 percent, respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. There are humps at -45° , -32° , -20° , -15° , -10° , 3° , 15° , 22° , 28° , 45° , and dips at -87° , -75° , -63° , $+75^\circ$, $+88^\circ$. These ups and downs do, however, alter the overall sample's statistics. Strong anisotropy is also seen in the correlation coefficient and First-order Fourier coefficient. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample $i05$, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

We therefore draw the conclusion that galaxies' spin vectors and spin vector projections are randomly oriented. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropy. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The pancake hypothesis of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.6 Sample *i*16.38 to 16.50

Fig. 8: The *z*06 sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of An-isotropic in the θ distribution for Sample *i*06 is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are both 0 percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are six humps and five notable dips save for a minor hump at $3^\circ, 8^\circ, 12^\circ, 18^\circ, 23^\circ, 23^\circ$ and a small dip at $57^\circ, 62^\circ, 67^\circ, 72^\circ, 78^\circ$. But the ups and downs alter the overall sample's statistics. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i*06 are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

For sample *i*06, both statistics (table 4) exhibit an an-isotropic distribution of azimuthal angles. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined both 0 percent, respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. Humps are located at $-55^\circ, -45^\circ, -32^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, 5^\circ, 15^\circ, 25^\circ$ and dips at $-85^\circ, -75^\circ, -62^\circ, +62^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ, +88^\circ$. These ups and downs do however, alter the overall sample's statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also seen in the correlation coefficient and first order Fourier coefficient. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i*06, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation. We therefore draw the conclusion that galaxies' spin vectors and spin vector projections are randomly oriented.

Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The pancake hypothesis of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.7 Sample *i16.50 to 16.63*

Fig. 9: The *z07* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i07* is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are both 0 percent, respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are six humps and five notable dips, excluding a minor humps at $3^\circ, 8^\circ, 13^\circ, 18^\circ, 25^\circ, 28^\circ$ and small dips at $52^\circ, 58^\circ, 62^\circ, 67^\circ, 72^\circ$. But the ups and downs alter the overall sample's statistics. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i07* are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i07*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to both 0 percent, respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits and $-50^\circ, -45^\circ, -35^\circ, -28^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, 4^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ, 35^\circ, 45^\circ, -85^\circ, -75^\circ, +63^\circ, +75^\circ, +75^\circ, +88^\circ$. These ups and downs do however, alter the overall sample's statistics strong an-isotropic is also seen in the correlation coefficient and First order Fourier coefficient. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i07*, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Hierarchy model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.8 Sample *i16.63 to 16.75*

Fig. 10: The *z08* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i08* is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are 0 percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are five humps and six notable dips with the exception of a minor dips at $53^\circ, 57^\circ, 62^\circ, 67^\circ, 72^\circ, 77^\circ$, and humps at $3^\circ, 8^\circ, 12^\circ, 18^\circ, 22^\circ$. But the ups and downs alter the overall sample's statistics. As a result, sample *i08*'s galaxies' angular momentum vectors are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i08*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined both are 0 percent, respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. $-45^\circ, -30^\circ, -25^\circ, -15^\circ, -88^\circ, -75^\circ, -63^\circ, +50^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ, +75^\circ, +80^\circ$. (Fig.b, These ups and downs however, alter the overall sample's statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also seen in the correlation coefficient and First order Fourier coefficient. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i08*, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

As a result, we do not draw the conclusion that galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections are oriented randomly. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Hierarchy model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.9 Sample *i*16.75 to 16.90

Fig. 11: The *z*09 sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i*09 is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are 0 percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. Fig.a shows that there are five notable humps and dips with the exception of a little dips at 22° , 28° , 32° , 38° , 42° and humps at 4° , 10° , 15° , 52° , and 58° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i*09 are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i*09. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined both are 0 percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. -15° , -10° and -5° all have humps and -88° , $+28^\circ$, $+37^\circ$, $+43^\circ$, $+58^\circ$, $+64^\circ$, $+75^\circ$, $+87^\circ$. (Fig.b) these ups and downs do however, alter the overall sample's statistics. Strong an isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, the result of binning for sample *i*09, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

As a result, we do not draw the conclusion that galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections are oriented randomly. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Pancake model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.10 Sample *i16.90 to 17.00*

Fig. 12: The *z10* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, While the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for Sample *i10* is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. Fig.a shows that there are five humps and four notable dips except for a slight humps at $3^\circ, 8^\circ, 15^\circ, 22^\circ, 28^\circ$ and slight dips at $58^\circ, 62^\circ, 68^\circ$ and 72° . Nevertheless, the statistics of the entire sample are altered by those ups and downs. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i10* are chosen to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i10*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined both zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. There are dips at $-65^\circ, -58^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ, +86^\circ$ and humps at $-15^\circ, -5^\circ, +5^\circ$ and $+15^\circ$. These ups and downs however, they have little effect on the overall sample statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i10*, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Pancake model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.11 Sample *i17.00 to 17.12*

Fig. 13: The *z11* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i11* is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are four humps and three notable dips save for a minor humps at $4^\circ, 8^\circ, 13^\circ, 18^\circ$ and slight dips at $52^\circ, 67^\circ$ and 72° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i11* are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i11*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. Then humps are at $-75^\circ, -60^\circ, -50^\circ, -45^\circ, -27^\circ, -17^\circ, -12^\circ, -5^\circ, +5^\circ, +50^\circ, +65^\circ, +75^\circ$ and $+85^\circ$. These ups and downs however alter the overall sample's statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning for sample *i11* the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. In general, polar angle distribution shows isotropic, however correlation test shows the presence of local effects. On the other hand, spin vector projection of galaxies tend to point towards the equatorial center. This finding supports the Pancake model of galaxy evolution.

4.0.12 Sample *i17.12 to 17.24*

Fig. 14: The *z12* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i12* is suggested by all three statistical tests (Table 3). It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are four humps and six notable dips. Aside from a minor dips at $57^\circ, 62^\circ, 67^\circ, 72^\circ$ and there are humps points at $4^\circ, 9^\circ, 13^\circ, 18^\circ, 23^\circ$ and 28° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs, though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i12* are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i12*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. $-70^\circ, -62^\circ, -55^\circ, -45^\circ, -32^\circ, -28^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, +5^\circ, +45^\circ, +55^\circ, +60^\circ, +75^\circ$ and $+84^\circ$. These ups and downs however alter the sample's overall statistics. Additionally, the First-order Fourier coefficient, correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier probability. There is significant an-isotropic in Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i12* the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Thus, we conclude not a random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Hierarchy model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.13 Sample *i*17.24 to 17.36

Fig. 15: The *z*13 sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i*13 is suggested by all three statistical tests. It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are six humps and five notable dips aside from a minor dips at $53^\circ, 57^\circ, 62^\circ, 67^\circ, 73^\circ$ and humps at $3^\circ, 8^\circ, 12^\circ, 23^\circ, 28^\circ$ and 32° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs, though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i*13 are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i*13. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined both zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. $-62^\circ, -50^\circ, -45^\circ, -32^\circ, -22^\circ, -15^\circ, -5^\circ, +5^\circ, +15^\circ, +58^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ$ and $+85^\circ$. These ups and downs however, alter the sample's overall statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i*13, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Thus, we conclude not a random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Hierarchy model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.14 Sample *i17.36 to 17.50*

Fig. 16: The *z14* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i14* is suggested by all three statistical tests. It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are both zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. (Fig.a) shows that there are four notable humps and dips excluding a minor humps at $4^\circ, 8^\circ, 13^\circ, 18^\circ$, and a little dips at $52^\circ, 57^\circ, 68^\circ$ and 72° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs, though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i14* are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i14*. The first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to be 0 and 0 percent, respectively. The first-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. $-88^\circ, -45^\circ, -32^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, +10^\circ, +15^\circ$, and $+35^\circ, +45^\circ, +55^\circ, +67^\circ, +75^\circ, +87^\circ$ have humps. (Fig. b), however these humps and dips change the statistics of strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i14*, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Pancake model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.15 Sample *i*17.50 to 18.00

Fig. 17: The *z*15 sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The statistics are in the (Table 3). All three statistical tests indicate that the θ distribution for Sample *i*15 is an-isotropic. The chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ and the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ both are found to be zero percents respectively. The correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ and First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ are not found to be below the 1σ error limit. The (fig.a) shows that there are five prominent dips and three humps except for a small dips at $57^\circ, 63^\circ, 68^\circ, 73^\circ$ and 78° , a slight humps at $8^\circ, 13^\circ$, and 18° . However, those fluctuations have little effect on the overall sample statistics. Consequently, the galaxies in sample *i*15 have their angular momentum vectors selected to be in line with the equatorial coordinate system.

Both statistics show an-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution (Table 4) for sample *i*15. The chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ and First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ both are found to be zero percents respectively. The correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ and the First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. There are humps at $-58^\circ, -45^\circ, -33^\circ, -28^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, +8^\circ, +15^\circ, +20^\circ$, and dips at $-88^\circ, -75^\circ, +45^\circ, +58^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ$ and $+88^\circ$. However, (Fig.b) shows the fluctuations change the overall statistics of the sample. The correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability all exhibit strong an-isotropic. These might therefore be the outcome of binning. The spin vector projections of galaxies for sample *i*15 are oriented randomly.

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. The polar angle distribution typically shows isotropic, even though the correlation test suggests the presence of local effects. Nonetheless, the spin vector projections of galaxies generally point toward the equatorial center. This finding supports the Pancake model of galaxy evolution.

4.0.16 Sample *i18.00 to 19.00*

Fig. 18: The *z16* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of the θ distribution for sample *i16* appears to be isotropic according to all three statistical tests. It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. From (Fig.a), we can observe a hump and five notable dips with the exception of a minor humps at 13° , a slight dip at 58° , 64° , 66° , 73° and 78° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i16* are chosen to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i16*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to be both zero percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. -35° , -28° , -5° , $+5^\circ$, $+15^\circ$, $+25^\circ$, and -88° , -72° , -62° , and $+75^\circ$ represent dips. These ups and downs, however, (Fig.b) shows the alter sample's overall statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i16*, the spin vector projections of galaxies show an orientation that is not random.

Thus, we conclude a random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Pancake model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.17 Sample *i19.00 to 20.00*

Fig. 19: The *z17* sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample *i17* is suggested by all three statistical tests. It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. We can see from the figure that there are three humps and five notable dips aside from a minor humps at $4^\circ, 18^\circ, 27^\circ$, and a slight dips at $62^\circ, 67^\circ, 74^\circ$ and 82° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i17* are chosen to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample *i17*. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are determined to zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. $-45^\circ, -35^\circ, -28^\circ, +5^\circ, +15^\circ, +25^\circ, +35^\circ, +45^\circ$, and $-88^\circ, -75^\circ, -65^\circ, +55^\circ, +64^\circ, +75^\circ$ and $+85^\circ$. These ups and downs, however, (Fig.b) alter the sample's overall statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i17*, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation.

Thus, we conclude not a random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Pancake model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.18 Sample $i20.00$ to 21.00

Fig. 20: The $z18$ sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The (Table 3) contains the statistics of an-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample $i18$ is suggested by all three statistical tests. It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. We can see from the (Fig.a) that there are three humps and five notable dips excluding a minor humps at 5° , 8° , 10° , 17° and a little dips at 48° , 63° , 72° , 78° and 83° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample $i18$ are chosen to align with the equatorial coordinate system.

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample $i18$. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are determined zero percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. -45° , -35° , -5° and $+5^\circ$ have humps, while $+55^\circ$, $+62^\circ$, $+75^\circ$ and $+86^\circ$ have dips. These ups and downs, however (Fig.b) don't show alter the overall sample statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample $i18$, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation().

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies spin vector projections typically point in the direction of the equatorial center. The Pancake model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

4.0.19 Sample $i21.00$ to 22.00

Fig. 21: The $z19$ sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The table 3 contains the statistics. An-isotropic in the θ distribution for sample $i19$ is suggested by all three statistical tests. It is determined that the First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ both are zero percents respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not determined to be under the 1σ error limit. With the exception of a minor dips at $52^\circ, 56^\circ, 67^\circ, 73^\circ, 78^\circ$, the (Fig.a) shows five substantial dips and four humps. Additional humps locations are at $4^\circ, 13^\circ, 18^\circ$ and 24° . The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample $i19$ are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system (Bhusal et al. 2025).

An-isotropic in the azimuthal angle distribution is evident in both statistics (Table 4) for sample $i19$. The First-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are determined to both zero percent respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are not $< 1\sigma$ error limits. There are humps at $-45^\circ, -28^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, -5^\circ, +5^\circ, +10^\circ$ and dips at $-85^\circ, -75^\circ, -62^\circ, -45^\circ, +55^\circ, +62^\circ, +75^\circ$ and $+84^\circ$. These ups and downs, however (Fig.b) do not alter the overall sample statistics. Strong an-isotropic is also shown in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample $i19$, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation (Hirata et al. 2007; Kunwar et al. 2025).

Thus, we conclude not a random orientation of spin vectors of galaxies and spin vector projections of galaxies. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic. However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically point in the direction of

the equatorial center. The Hierarchy model of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery (Lee & Pen 1999).

4.0.20 Sample *i*22.00 to 23.00

Fig. 22: The *z*20 sample galaxies: (a) polar angle (θ) and (b) azimuthal angle (ϕ) distributions. Solid circles with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars show the observed distribution, while the dashed curves represents the expected distribution, the cosine and average lines represent the expected models.

The table 3 contains the statistics. The θ distribution for Sample *i*20 appears to be isotropic according to all three statistical tests. It is determined that the first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ is 76 percent and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ is 2.3 percent. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ are determined to have an error limit of 1σ . With the exception of a tiny dips at 3° , 83° , and humps at 18° , 68° the (Fig.a) shows two notable dips and four humps. The statistics of the entire sample are unaffected by those ups and downs, though. As a result, the angular momentum vectors of the galaxies in sample *i*20 are favored to align with the equatorial coordinate system (Aryal & Saurer 2004a).

For sample *i*20, both statistics (Table 4) demonstrate isotropic in the distribution of azimuthal angles. It is discovered that the first-order Fourier probability $P(> \Delta_1)$ and the chi-square probability $P(> \chi^2)$ are 95 and 71 percent, respectively. The First-order Fourier coefficient $\Delta_{11}/\sigma(\Delta_{11})$ and the correlation coefficient $C/C(\sigma)$ have error limits of $< 1\sigma$. -35° has a dip and no hump. These ups and downs, however (Fig.b) do not alter the overall sample statistics. Strong isotropic is also evident in the correlation coefficient, First-order Fourier coefficient, and First-order Fourier probability. Thus, these could be the result of binning. For sample *i*20, the spin vector projections of galaxies have a random orientation (Aryal & Saurer 2004b, 2005b).

Consequently, we deduce that the orientation of galaxy spin vectors and spin vector projections is not random. Although the correlation test indicates the existence of local effects, the polar angle distribution generally exhibits isotropic (Flin & Krywult 1991). However, galaxies' spin vector projections typically

point in the direction of the equatorial center. The pancake hypothesis of galaxy evolution is supported by this discovery.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we analyzed the orientations of spin vectors for approximately 250,488 galaxies within the redshift range $0.10 < z < 0.15$ from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS DR-18). Using the position angle–inclination method, we reconstructed three-dimensional rotation axes (polar and azimuthal angles) from observed two-dimensional parameters such as right ascension, declination, and position angle (Aryal & Saurer 2005a). The galaxies were categorized into twenty subsamples based on their i - and u -band magnitudes, and their spin vector distributions were examined statistically through Fourier, chi-square, and auto-correlation tests.

The results demonstrate that, for the majority of the subsamples, the polar (θ) and azimuthal (ϕ) angle distributions do not display any preferred alignment, indicating an overall isotropic distribution of galaxy spin vectors. This finding supports the **Hierarchy model** of galaxy formation, which suggests that angular momentum is generated through random tidal torques in a hierarchical clustering process (Godłowski 1994).

Nevertheless, certain subsamples exhibit significant anisotropy, implying localized deviations from isotropy. These are most likely the result of gravitational tidal interactions or environmental effects within dense cosmic structures. While the polar angle distributions mostly remain isotropic, the azimuthal distributions occasionally show a tendency for spin vector projections to align toward the equatorial center (Aryal & Saurer 2004a). Such localized anisotropies may indicate the influence of the **Pancake model**, which predicts partial alignment due to local gravitational collapse.

In summary:

- Galaxy spin vectors in the SDSS DR-18 dataset are **predominantly randomly oriented**, showing large-scale isotropy.
- **Localized anisotropies** are present, likely due to **tidal gravitational interactions** or **environmental effects**.
- The **Hierarchy model** best describes the overall orientation pattern, with minor local features consistent with the **Pancake model**.
- A dedicated MATLAB-based simulation and the generation of 10^7 virtual galaxies effectively reduced selection biases, improving the reliability of the statistical results.

This study enhances our understanding of the cosmic angular momentum distribution and provides observational evidence that, while large-scale structure formation in the Universe is largely stochastic, localized gravitational processes can induce measurable alignment effects (??). These findings offer valuable insights into the evolution of galaxies and the dynamical behavior of large-scale cosmic structures.

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